

A wind tunnel setup to measure aeroelastic airfoil gust response

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Gust disturbance presents a significant challenge for modern aerodynamic structures, especially as wings become lighter, feature higher aspect ratios and exhibit increased structural flexibility. As a result of fluid-structure interactions involving flow separation, aeroelastic effects emerge, requiring advanced methodologies beyond classic potential flow-based approaches. To address these challenges, the present study presents the design and commissioning of a wind tunnel setup capable of investigating the gust response of elastically mounted airfoils at Reynolds numbers $Re \geq 1M$.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the wind tunnel setup at NTUA. A vane-type gust generator (GG) is combined with an elastic setup that enables the assessment of aeroelastic effects, particularly at initial angles of attack exceeding the static stall limit, where flow separation becomes dominant². The gusts interact with the elastically mounted airfoil model, which is supported by torsional and bending springs of stiffness k_a and k_h . The GG and vane motion protocol was assisted by CFD simulations using the in-house computational fluid dynamics solver MaPFlow¹. A new motion protocol is proposed to reduce the unwanted negative excursions of the generated perturbation (see Figure 2, left). At the time of writing, preliminary results are available and displayed in Figure 2, (right), with a more in-depth analysis to be shared at the conference.

Figure 1: Schematic of the experimental setup

Figure 2: (left) 2D RANS investigation on vane motion. Comparison with ‘1-cos’ and motion presented by Balatti et al.³. (right) Experiment, 2D RANS. Flow angle 10 chords downstream of the GG vanes. ‘1-cos’ motion. $U_\infty=10$ m/s, $A=20^\circ$, $f=10$ Hz.

Acknowledgements The research project is implemented in the framework of H.F.R.I call “Basic research Financing (Horizontal support of all Sciences)” under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan “Greece 2.0” funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU (H.F.R.I. Project Number:016749)

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¹Papadakis, G. and Voutsinas, S. G., *Comput. Fluids* **195**, 104325 (2019)

²Gkiolas, D, *Natl. Tech. Univ. Athens*, PhD Thesis (2022)

³Balatti, D et al., *J. Aircr.* **59(6)**, 1514-1528 (2022)